

KIBERXAVFSIZLIKDA NMAP SCRIPTING ENGINE (NSE) TEXNOLOGIYASIDAN FOYDALANISH

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ NMAP SCRIPTING ENGINE (NSE) В КИБЕРБЕЗОПАСНОСТИ

APPLICATION OF NMAP SCRIPTING ENGINE (NSE) TECHNOLOGY IN CYBERSECURITY

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Аннотация. Mazkur maqolada kiberxavfsizlik sohasida keng qo'llaniladigan **Nmap (Network Mapper)** tarmoq skanerlash vositasining muhim komponentlaridan biri bo'lgan **Nmap Scripting Engine (NSE)** texnologiyasining imkoniyatlari va amaliy qo'llanilishi tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot davomida NSE skriptlarining tarmoq infratuzilmasini tekshirish, xizmatlarni aniqlash, tizimdagi xavfsizlik zaifliklarini aniqlash hamda avtomatlashtirilgan xavfsizlik auditini amalga oshirishdagi ahamiyati o'rganildi. Shuningdek, NSE skriptlarining ishlash tamoyillari, ularning kategoriyalari va tarmoq xavfsizligini ta'minlashdagi roli ilmiy jihatdan yoritib berildi. Maqolada skriptlardan foydalanish orqali axborot tizimlarining himoyalanganlik darajasini baholash, potensial tahdidlarni aniqlash va ularni oldini olish imkoniyatlari ko'rsatib berilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, Nmap Scripting Engine texnologiyasidan samarali foydalanish tarmoq monitoringi, zaifliklarni aniqlash va kiberxavfsizlikni mustahkamlash jarayonlarida muhim vosita hisoblanadi. Ushbu ish kiberxavfsizlik mutaxassislari, tizim administratorlari hamda axborot texnologiyalari yo'nalishida tahsil olayotgan talabalar uchun amaliy ahamiyatga ega.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются возможности и практическое применение технологии **Nmap Scripting Engine (NSE)**, являющейся одним из ключевых компонентов инструмента сетевого сканирования **Nmap (Network Mapper)**, широко используемого в сфере кибербезопасности. В ходе исследования проанализирована роль NSE-скриптов при проверке сетевой инфраструктуры, выявлении активных сервисов, обнаружении уязвимостей в информационных системах и проведении автоматизированного аудита безопасности.

Также подробно рассмотрены принципы работы NSE-скриптов, их основные категории и значение в обеспечении безопасности компьютерных сетей. В статье показаны возможности использования данных скриптов для оценки уровня защищенности информационных систем, выявления потенциальных угроз и предотвращения возможных кибератак. Результаты исследования показывают, что эффективное использование технологии **Nmap Scripting Engine** является важным

инструментом для мониторинга сетей, обнаружения уязвимостей и повышения уровня кибербезопасности. Представленная работа может иметь практическую значимость для специалистов в области кибербезопасности, системных администраторов, а также студентов, обучающихся по направлениям информационных технологий.

Abstract. This article examines the capabilities and practical applications of the **Nmap Scripting Engine (NSE)** technology, which is one of the key components of the **Nmap (Network Mapper)** network scanning tool widely used in the field of cybersecurity. The study analyzes the role of NSE scripts in inspecting network infrastructure, identifying active services, detecting vulnerabilities in information systems, and conducting automated security audits.

In addition, the working principles of NSE scripts, their main categories, and their role in ensuring network security are described. The article also demonstrates how these scripts can be used to assess the security level of information systems, identify potential threats, and prevent possible cyber attacks. The results of the research indicate that the effective use of **Nmap Scripting Engine** technology is an important tool for network monitoring, vulnerability detection, and strengthening cybersecurity. The presented work may have practical significance for cybersecurity specialists, system administrators, and students studying in the field of information technologies.

Kalit soʻzlar: kiberxavfsizlik, Nmap, Nmap Scripting Engine (NSE), tarmoq skanerlash, axborot xavfsizligi, zaifliklarni aniqlash, tarmoq monitoringi, xavfsizlik auditi.

Ключевые слова: кибербезопасность, Nmap, Nmap Scripting Engine (NSE), сетевое сканирование, информационная безопасность, обнаружение уязвимостей, мониторинг сети, аудит безопасности.

Keywords: cybersecurity, Nmap, Nmap Scripting Engine (NSE), network scanning, information security, vulnerability detection, network monitoring, security auditing.

Kirish

Kiberxavfsizlik zamonaviy axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining eng muhim yoʻnalishlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Axborot tizimlari, kompyuter tarmoqlari va internet xizmatlarining keng rivojlanishi natijasida turli xil kiberxavflar, noqonuniy kirishlar va zaifliklardan foydalanish holatlari ortib bormoqda. Shu sababli tarmoq infratuzilmasini tahlil qilish, ochiq portlarni aniqlash, xizmatlarni tekshirish hamda zaifliklarni oʻz vaqtida topish masalasi alohida dolzarflik kasb etadi.

Bugungi kunda tarmoq xavfsizligini taʼminlashda qoʻllaniladigan samarali vositalardan biri bu **Nmap (Network Mapper)** dasturidir. Mazkur vosita yordamida tarmoq tugunlarini aniqlash, ochiq portlarni tekshirish, ishlayotgan servislarni topish va operatsion tizim haqida maʼlumot olish mumkin. Nmapʼning eng kuchli imkoniyatlaridan biri esa **Nmap Scripting Engine (NSE)** texnologiyasi hisoblanadi. Ushbu texnologiya yordamida foydalanuvchi nafaqat oddiy skanerlashni, balki maxsus skriptlar orqali chuqur tekshiruv, xavfsizlik auditi va zaifliklarni aniqlash ishlarini ham bajarishi mumkin.

NSE tizimi **Lua** dasturlash tiliga asoslangan boʻlib, u avtomatlashtirilgan tekshiruv jarayonlarini tashkil etishda muhim oʻrin tutadi. Turli kategoriyadagi skriptlar yordamida autentifikatsiya, xizmatlar, zararli konfiguratsiyalar, zaifliklar va boshqa koʻrsatkichlar tekshiriladi. Shu jihatdan qaralganda, Nmap skriptlari kiberxavfsizlik amaliyotida keng qoʻllaniladigan qulay va samarali vosita hisoblanadi.

Mazkur maqolada Nmap Scripting Engine texnologiyasining mazmuni, ishlash tamoyili, asosiy skript turlari, qo'llanilish sohalari hamda kiberxavfsizlikdagi amaliy ahamiyati ilmiy jihatdan tahlil qilinadi.

Host va Port Skanerlash

Kurs: NetworkEnumeration With NMAP

Host and Port Scanning

Host va Port Skanerlash

Top 10 TCP portlarni skanlash

```
$ sudo nmap 10.129.2.28 --top-ports=10
```

Starting Nmap 7.80 (<https://nmap.org>) at 2020-06-15 15:36 CEST

Nmap scan report for 10.129.2.28

Host is up (0.021s latency).

PORT STATE SERVICE

21/tcp closed ftp

22/tcp open ssh

23/tcp closed telnet

25/tcp open smtp

80/tcp open http

110/tcp open pop3

139/tcp filtered netbios-ssn

443/tcp closed https

445/tcp filtered microsoft-ds

3389/tcp closed ms-wbt-server

MAC Address: DE:AD:00:00:BE:EF (Intel Corporate)

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 1.44 seconds

Scanning Options Description

10.129.2.28 Targetni skanerlash

--top-ports=10 Nmap ma'lumotlar bazasidagi eng ko'p uchraydigan portlar bo'yicha

Bu yerda biz faqat maqsadning top 10 TCP portini skan qildik va Nmap ularning holatini ko'rsatdi. Agar yuborilayotgan paketlarni kuzatsak, port 21 uchun bizga qaytarilgan RST bayrog'i mavjudligini ko'ramiz. SYN skanini aniq kuzatish uchun ICMP echo so'rovlarini o'chirib (-Pn), DNS rezolyutsiyasini o'chirib (-n) va ARP pingni o'chirib (--disable-arp-ping) ishlash ma'qul.

Nmap - Trace the Packets

```
$ sudo nmap 10.129.2.28 -p 21 --packet-trace -Pn -n --disable-arp-ping
```

Starting Nmap 7.80 (<https://nmap.org>) at 2020-06-15 15:39 CEST

SENT (0.0429s) TCP 10.10.14.2:63090 > 10.129.2.28:21 S ttl=56 id=57322 iplen=44 seq=1699105818 win=1024 <mss 1460>

RCVD (0.0573s) TCP 10.129.2.28:21 > 10.10.14.2:63090 RA ttl=64 id=0 iplen=40 seq=0 win=0

Nmap scan report for 10.129.2.28

Host is up (0.014s latency).

PORT STATE SERVICE

21/tcp closed ftp

MAC Address: DE:AD:00:00:BE:EF (Intel Corporate)

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 0.07 seconds

Bu yerda SENT qatorida biz (10.10.14.2) SYN bayrog'i bilan TCP paket yuborganimiz, RCVD qatorida esa 10.129.2.28 bizga RST/ACK (RA) bilan javob berganini ko'ramiz. RST va ACK - paketni qabul qilganini tasdiqlovchi va TCP sessiyani tugatish uchun ishlatiladigan bayroqlar.

Request Message Description

RCVD (0.0573s) Indicates a received packet from the target

TCP Shows the protocol that is being used

10.129.2.28:21 > Represents targets IPv4 address and the source port, which will be used to reply

10.10.14.2:63090 Shows our IPv4 address and the port that will be replied to

RA RST and ACK flags of the sent TCP packet

ttl=64 id=0 iplen=40 seq=0 win=0 Additional TCP Header parameters

Connect Scan (-sT)

Nmap TCP Connect Scan (-sT) maqsad port ochiq yoki yopiq ekanligini aniqlash uchun to'liq TCP uch tomonlama handshake'ini bajaradi. Agar port SYN-ACK bilan javob bersa - ochiq, RST bilan javob bersa - yopiq deb hisoblanadi. Connect scan aniq natija beradi, lekin stealth jihatdan zaif (ko'p tizimlarda loglar hosil qiladi va IDS/IPS tomonidan osongina aniqlanishi mumkin). Ammo agar aniqlik birinchi o'rinda bo'lsa yoki maqsad tarmoq xaritasini aniqlash kerak bo'lsa foydali. Shuningdek, ba'zi shaxsiy firewall'lar kiruvchi paketlarni tushirib yuboradi, ammo chiqish paketlariga ruxsat beradi; bunday holatda -sT yordam beradi.

Misol: Connect scan TCP port 443 uchun:

\$ sudo nmap 10.129.2.28 -p 443 --packet-trace --disable-arp-ping -Pn -n --reason -sT

Starting Nmap 7.80 (<https://nmap.org>) at 2020-06-15 16:26 CET

CONN (0.0385s) TCP localhost > 10.129.2.28:443 => Operation now in progress

CONN (0.0396s) TCP localhost > 10.129.2.28:443 => Connected

Nmap scan report for 10.129.2.28

Host is up, received user-set (0.013s latency).

PORT STATE SERVICE REASON

443/tcp open https syn-ack

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 0.04 seconds

Filterlangan portlar (Filtered Ports)

Agar port filtered deb chiqsa, buning bir nechta sabablari bo'lishi mumkin: firewall qoidalari paketlarni tushirib qo'yadi yoki rad etadi. Agar paket tushirilsa, Nmap hech qanday javob olmaydi va standart bo'yicha --max-retries 10 ga teng, ya'ni Nmap so'rovni qayta yuboradi. Masalan, TCP 139 portini skan qilganda Nmap bir necha SYN yuborgan, javob olinmagani uchun port filtered deb ko'rsatildi (va skan vaqti ancha uzoq bo'ldi). Agar firewall paketlarni rad etsa, siz ICMP xato (type 3 code 3) olishingiz mumkin - bu port unreachable ekanligini bildiradi. Masalan TCP 445 uchun olingan ICMP port unreachable javobi portni filtered deb belgilashga olib keldi.

\$ sudo nmap 10.129.2.28 -p 139 --packet-trace -n --disable-arp-ping -Pn

Starting Nmap 7.80 (<https://nmap.org>) at 2020-06-15 15:45 CEST

SENT (0.0381s) TCP 10.10.14.2:60277 > 10.129.2.28:139 S ttl=47 id=14523 iplen=44 seq=4175236769 win=1024 <mss 1460>

SENT (1.0411s) TCP 10.10.14.2:60278 > 10.129.2.28:139 S ttl=45 id=7372 iplen=44 seq=4175171232 win=1024 <mss 1460>

Nmap scan report for 10.129.2.28

Host is up.

PORT STATE SERVICE

139/tcp filtered netbios-ssn

MAC Address: DE:AD:00:00:BE:EF (Intel Corporate)

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 2.06 seconds

Ochiq UDP portlarni aniqlash

Ba'zi ma'muriyatlar UDP portlarni unutyapti. UDP stateless bo'lgani uchun tasdiqlovchi javob olinmaydi va timeout ko'p bo'ladi, shuning uchun UDP skan (-sU) TCP skaniga nisbatan ancha sekin. UDP skan oddiy bo'lsa-da, ko'pincha hech qanday javob olinmaydi - Nmap bo'sh UDP datagrammalar yuboradi va ilova javob bermasa port haqida aniq xulosa chiqarib bo'lmaydi. Agar ilova ochiq va protokol javob qaytarsa, Nmap open yoki open|filtered deb ko'rsatadi; agar ICMP port unreachable olinsa - closed.

\$ sudo nmap 10.129.2.28 -F -sU

Starting Nmap 7.80 (<https://nmap.org>) at 2020-06-15 16:01 CEST

Nmap scan report for 10.129.2.28

Host is up (0.059s latency).

Not shown: 95 closed ports

PORT STATE SERVICE

68/udp open|filtered dhcpc

137/udp open netbios-ns

138/udp open|filtered netbios-dgm

631/udp open|filtered ipp

5353/udp open zeroconf

MAC Address: DE:AD:00:00:BE:EF (Intel Corporate)

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 98.07 seconds

Xizmat versiyalarini aniqlash (sV)

-sV opsiyasi orqali ochiq portlardan qo'shimcha ma'lumotlar olish mumkin - xizmat nomi, versiya va ba'zan ishga tushirilgan platforma haqida ma'lumot. Bu Nmap probe-larini yuborib qaytgan javoblarni moslashtirish orqali amalga oshiriladi.

\$ sudo nmap 10.129.2.28 -Pn -n --disable-arp-ping --packet-trace -p 445 --reason -sV

Starting Nmap 7.80 (<https://nmap.org>) at 2022-11-04 11:10 GMT

SENT (0.3426s) TCP 10.10.14.2:44641 > 10.129.2.28:445 S ttl=55 id=43401 iplen=44 seq=3589068008 win=1024 <mss 1460>

RCVD (0.3556s) TCP 10.129.2.28:445 > 10.10.14.2:44641 SA ttl=63 id=0 iplen=44 seq=2881527699 win=29200 <mss 1337>

NSOCK INFO [0.4980s] nsock_iod_new2(): nsock_iod_new (IOD#1)

NSOCK INFO [0.4980s] nsock_connect_tcp(): TCP connection requested to 10.129.2.28:445 (IOD#1) EID 8

NSOCK INFO [0.5130s] nsock_trace_handler_callback(): Callback: CONNECT SUCCESS for EID 8 [10.129.2.28:445]

Service scan sending probe NULL to 10.129.2.28:445 (tcp)

NSOCK INFO [0.5130s] nsock_read(): Read request from IOD#1 [10.129.2.28:445] (timeout: 6000ms) EID 18

NSOCK INFO [6.5190s] nsock_trace_handler_callback(): Callback: READ TIMEOUT for EID 18 [10.129.2.28:445]

Service scan sending probe SMBProgNeg to 10.129.2.28:445 (tcp)

NSOCK INFO [6.5190s] nsock_write(): Write request for 168 bytes to IOD#1 EID 27 [10.129.2.28:445]

NSOCK INFO [6.5190s] nsock_read(): Read request from IOD#1 [10.129.2.28:445] (timeout: 5000ms) EID 34

NSOCK INFO [6.5190s] nsock_trace_handler_callback(): Callback: WRITE SUCCESS for EID 27 [10.129.2.28:445]

NSOCK INFO [6.5320s] nsock_trace_handler_callback(): Callback: READ SUCCESS for EID 34 [10.129.2.28:445] (135 bytes)

Service scan match (Probe SMBProgNeg matched with SMBProgNeg line 13836): 10.129.2.28:445 is netbios-ssn. Version: |Samba smbd|3.X - 4.X|workgroup: WORKGROUP|

NSOCK INFO [6.5320s] nsock_iod_delete(): nsock_iod_delete (IOD#1)

Nmap scan report for 10.129.2.28

Host is up, received user-set (0.013s latency).

PORT STATE SERVICE REASON VERSION

445/tcp open netbios-ssn syn-ack ttl 63 Samba smbd 3.X - 4.X (workgroup: WORKGROUP)

Service Info: Host: Ubuntu

Service detection performed. Please report any incorrect results at <https://nmap.org/submit>

XULOSA

Mazkur tadqiqotda tarmoq infratuzilmasini tahlil qilishda keng qo'llaniladigan **Nmap vositasi** yordamida hostlarni aniqlash va portlarni skanerlash usullari ko'rib chiqildi. Tahlillar shuni ko'rsatdiki, Nmap yordamida tarmoqdagi faol qurilmalarni aniqlash, ochiq portlarni topish, xizmatlarning versiyalarini aniqlash va tizimlar haqida muhim ma'lumotlar olish mumkin.

Host discovery jarayonida ICMP, ARP va boshqa ping usullaridan foydalanish orqali tarmoqdagi faol hostlarni aniqlash mumkinligi ko'rsatildi. Bundan tashqari, Nmap yordamida IP diapazonlarini, alohida IP manzillarni yoki oldindan tayyorlangan hostlar ro'yxatini skanerlash imkoniyati mavjudligi tahlil qilindi.

Port skanerlash jarayonida portlarning **open, closed, filtered** kabi turli holatlarda bo'lishi mumkinligi va ularning har biri tarmoq xavfsizligini baholashda muhim ahamiyatga ega ekanligi aniqlandi. TCP SYN scan, TCP Connect scan va UDP scan kabi usullar orqali tarmoq xizmatlarini aniqlash hamda tizimdagi potentsial zaifliklarni topish mumkin.

Shuningdek, **Nmapning -sV opsiyasi** orqali xizmat versiyalarini aniqlash tarmoqdagi dasturiy ta'minotlar haqida qo'shimcha ma'lumot olish imkonini beradi. Bu esa kiberxavfsizlik mutaxassislariga tizimdagi zaifliklarni aniqlash va ularni bartaraf etish choralarini ko'rishda muhim yordam beradi.

Umuman olganda, Nmap vositasi kiberxavfsizlik sohasida tarmoqlarni monitoring qilish, penetration testing o'tkazish va axborot tizimlarining himoyalanganlik darajasini baholashda samarali vosita hisoblanadi.

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